

Impact Factor:

ISSN: 2509-0119

JIF: 6.662

ICV: 80.38

IFSIJ : 7.625

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PROGRESSIVE SCIENCES AND TECHNOLOGIES

Vol. 25 N. 1 February 2021

International Journals

of Sciences and High Technologies

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English Explanation Of Medical Hybrid Terms With French Prefix "Anti"

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Abstract – This article provides a comparative analysis of medical terms used in French. This article examines French medical terms that begin with the prefix "anti", explained along with Uzbek alternatives.

Keywords – Terminology, Term, Medical Term, Hybrid, "Anti" Prefix, Medical Term, Neologism, Dictionary.

I. INTRODUCTION

The need for a responsible approach to the development of terminological systems of the Uzbek language is reflected in the following opinion of the first President I.A.Karimov: The publication of a large number of scientific and popular books, textbooks, dictionaries dedicated to the peculiarities of the society contributes to the development of public opinion. It is especially noteworthy that the state language is becoming an active means of communication at the international level. The fact that the Uzbek language is widely used in areas that require special terms and concepts, such as computers, the Internet, the exact sciences, medicine, economics, shows how great its potential is. ”

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Many scientists from around the world have been researching terminology for many years. U. Tursunov was one of the first to conduct a deeper study of the terminology of the Uzbek language. He is the author of such works as terminology, "Language - against the bourgeois aspirations in terminology", "Problems of Uzbek terminology", "Problems of terminology", "Principles of word-term selection in the Uzbek literary language".

Terminology as a science in the world The Austrian scientist O.V. Nubasov and the Russian scientist it dates back to D.S. Lotte's first work, published in 1930. Currently, terminology schools have emerged in countries such as Austria, Germany, France, Russia, and the Czech Republic.

The main purpose of the study of terms is to ensure the transparency of the language and the ability to use words from foreign languages, to replace them with words that exactly correspond to our language.

III. ANALYSIS

It is known that the Uzbek language has some components, such as Arabic, Persian, Russian and French. These terms have their own prefixes, suffixes and infixes. “Although some prefixes and suffixes are involved in the formation of a large number of hybrids (for example: -algia, anti-, -ectomy and -tomy, -gene, -graphy, hyper- and hypo;) has never been used in common medicine to form such terms, ”meaning that it refers to compound (hybrid) terms formed from word units belonging to different

languages. Some prefixes that enrich medical terminology are derived from Greek, Greek, and Latin and have their own meanings:

- *an* (**yun.** negative) → an + aima = du sang (blood) – anemie – chlorosis;
- *anti* (**grek.** antonym) → anti + pyrétique = combat la fièvre (fight fever) – - Antipyrétique - fever, lowering the temperature. The prefix term "anti" ("*en face de, contre et de onoma*"), which is essentially derived from the Greek language, serves to express opposite meanings. (4.46 (5));
- *bar* (Greek weight) → baros + mètre = mesure la pression (pressure gauge) - Barometer - a device that measures atmospheric pressure;
- *bio* (Greek bios) → bio + logie = science de la vie (life science) - Biologie - a set of sciences about living nature;
- *brady* (Greek slowly, slow) → brady + cardie = ralentissement du rythme cardiaque (slow heartbeat) - Bradycardie - slowing of heart contractions, slow (*less than 60 beats per minute*) heartbeat;
- *bronch* (Greek: breath) → bronch + ite = inflammation des bronches (bronchitis) - Bronchitis - inflammation of the respiratory organs;
- *cardi* (Greek: cardiovascular) → cardi + opathie = toute affection du coeur (heart disease);
- *caryo* (Greek cell) → caryo + type = ensemble des chromosomes de la cellule (cell set of chromosomes) - Caryotype - a set of chromosomes of an organism of a certain size, shape and number;
- *céphal* (Greek skull) → céphal + ées = douleurs à la tête, violentes et tenaces (headache, violent and constant) - Céphalées - feeling of pain in the head;
- *col* (Greek glove) → col + ique = douleur aigüe du côlon (acute colon pain) - Colique - inflammation of the colon and other similar prefixes contribute to the development of medical terms.

The prefix "anti" is a prefix to linguistic units that can form many hybrid compound medical terms that have opposite, opposite meanings.

And the anti prefix renews the meaning associated with the word. In words beginning with the letter "i", the vowel is connected by a dash (-) (anti (+) - inflammatoire = anti - inflammatoire). Dictionaries define this prefix as follows:

anti prefix - (Greek. anti - against, contradict) a suffix added to certain words from the front, denoting the opposite of what the word means (sign, action). (2.47);

anti prefix - (Greek) a prefix that means to be opposed to something, to be directed against it(1.41);

anti prefix - (Greek. anti - against, contradict) is added to certain words from the front, and the meaning of the word itself is the opposite of something (3,546);

anti prefix does not mean "against" but "instead". (11);

anti prefix Greek against, oppose, conflicting, contradictory, versus, agin, dissenting (4.46 (6)).

IV. DISCUSSION

Some words that begin with anti do not have opposite meanings: "antelope" - the name of an antelope (deer), "antiquité" - an ancient period, "antidater" - a verb; such as formalizing with a past, expired date (letter, document), (4, 46 (3)).

Here are some French medical terms that start with the prefix "**anti**":

In French	In Uzbek	Definition
<i>anti-adrénergiques</i>	<i>antiadrenergic agents</i> (<i>lot - antiadrenergy</i>)	adrenergic - drugs that prevent or eliminate the action of the sympathetic nerve;
<i>antiacide</i>	<i>antacids</i> (<i>anti and lot. aciditas - acid</i>)	drugs that are alkaline and are used to neutralize hydrochloric acid in gastric juice. Antacids include sodium bicarbonate, magnesium oxide, and other gastric juices for acid-induced gastritis, gastric, and duodenal ulcers.
<i>antibiotique (nm)</i>	<i>antibiotics</i>	organic substances, drugs that stop or kill some microbes and bacteria.
<i>anticorps (nm)</i>	<i>antibodies</i>	substances that are formed by the formation of antigens in the body and lose their effect.

<i>antisepsie (nf)</i>	<i>antiseptic</i>	decontamination of the wound with chemical drugs, protection from bites, pus.
<i>antitoxine (nf)</i>	<i>antitoxin (Greek)</i>	specific proteins (antibodies) that neutralize microorganism toxins (eg, tetanus, diphtheria A), plant toxins (ricin, abrin), and animal toxins (snake, blackbird venom).
<i>antitétanique (adj)</i> (- une piqûre <i>antitétanique</i>)	<i>antianemic agents (anemia)</i> (lat. <i>antianaemica</i>)	drugs used to treat anemia; (injection against anemia.)
<i>antirabique (adj)</i> (- vaccination <i>antirabique</i>)	<i>antirabic</i> (- antirabic vaccine)	anti-rabies, anti-rabies; (Repeated subcutaneous vaccination of a person infected with rabies to prevent rabies.)
<i>antibactériennes</i>	<i>antibacterial effect</i>	the effect of physical, chemical, or biological factors that have the property of killing or suppressing bacteria.
<i>antibiotiques</i>	<i>antibiotics - (anti. + Greek bios - life)</i>	substances that inhibit the growth and development of various microbes that are developed during the life of some microorganisms, animals and plants.
<i>anticoagulantes</i>	<i>anticoagulants (Greek, lot)</i>	blood clotting drugs.
<i>antirhumatismaux</i>	<i>antirheumatic agents (lot. antirheumatica)</i>	drugs with immunodepressive, anti-inflammatory and analgesic effects.
<i>antihelminthiques</i>	<i>anthelmintics</i> (anti and Greek. helmins - worm)	<i>Drugs used for the prevention and treatment of worm diseases in humans and animals: pipe-razin adipinate, chloxy, vermoz and others</i>
<i>antifongique</i>	<i>antifungal</i>	The antifungal drug is used to treat and prevent serious systemic infections such as candidiasis (nettle), cryptococcal meningitis and others.
<i>antimicrobiennes</i>	<i>antimicrobial agents (lat. antimierobica) -</i>	substances used to kill or disrupt microorganisms; antiseptics, disinfectants and other means.
<i>antimigraine</i>	antimigren (frans.anti + migraine)	<i>It is said to be a remedy for brain pain (hemicrania - occasional headache).</i>
<i>anti-obésité</i>	antihypertension	It is the most common (up to 75%) antihypertensive drug in humans.
<i>antigène (nm)</i> (-analyse d' <i>antigène</i>)	<i>antigen (anti ... + Greek genos - generation; origin)</i> (-antigen analysis)	When ingested, substances that can cause antibodies to develop in the blood and other tissues and build immunity. (Determination of antigenic properties of cells, tissues, microorganisms, etc. by conducting various serological reactions)
<i>antiprotozoaire</i>	<i>antiprotozoic (lot. antiprotozoica)</i>	drugs that stop the activity of simple animals and are used in the treatment of protozoal infections.
<i>antioxydants</i>	<i>antioxidants</i>	substances that prevent or attenuate oxidation by molecular oxygen, which are usually a necessary component of all tissues and cells in humans and animals;
<i>antiovulatoire</i>	<i>antiovulator</i> (lot. <i>antiavulatoryia</i>)	It is used to prevent pregnancy and to trace the menstrual cycle;
<i>antimutagenes</i>	<i>antimutagens</i> (Greek, lot)	Genetic changes in the body are chemical and medical factors that reduce the recurrence of mutations.

antialcoolique (adj)	<i>against alcohol</i>	against alcohol, against alcoholism; directed against alcoholism, drunkenness;
anticancéreux, euse (adj)	<i>anticancer</i>	anti-cancer, anti-cancer focused; aimed at combating cancer.
antidiphthérique (adj)	<i>antidifteria</i>	anti-asthma drugs.
antimite (adj)	<i>against moth</i>	naphthalene
antihormonales	<i>antihormonal substances (lot. antihormonalia)</i>	<i>drugs that have the property of blocking or weakening the action of hormones.</i>
antihistaminiques	<i>antihistamines</i>	drugs that partially or completely block the physiological effects of histamine; used in allergic reactions and skin diseases.
antidotes	<i>antidotes (Greek)</i>	<i>antidotes - drugs that neutralize toxins that enter the body.</i>
antituberculeux, -euse (adj) (- vaccin antituberculeux - un traitement antituberculeux)	<i>against tuberculosis (Greek. anti + tuberculosis)</i>	anti-tuberculosis, anti-tuberculosis; (- tuberculosis vaccine; - treatment of tuberculosis.)
antispasmodique	<i>antispasmodic</i>	I. (adj) against spasms, spasms, cramps, aches and pains; II. (nm) anticonvulsant drug.
antirides (adj)	<i>against wrinkles</i>	wrinkle, against wrinkle pressing; wrinkle remover;
anticonceptionnel, elle (adj)	<i>contraceptive tool</i>	Contraceptive.
anti-inflammatoire	<i>antiflogistics</i>	anti-inflammatory drugs;
antiangineux	<i>antianginal agents (lot. antianginalia)</i>	drugs that increase blood flow to the heart or reduce the heart's need for oxygen; used to prevent or suppress angina attacks;
antimétabolites	<i>antimetabolites (anti and Greek. metabole - change)</i>	substances that disrupt the absorption of intermediate compounds formed during metabolism in living organisms. It is a foreign substance to the body.
antipéristaltique	<i>antiperistaltika (ant. and Greek. peristaltikos - the force that pushes intestinal fluid)</i>	contraction of the esophagus, stomach and intestines from below.
antithrombine	<i>antithrombin (Greek. anti - anti + thrombin)</i>	the common name for a group of substances that are present in blood plasma and are considered antagonists of thrombin.
antivitamines	<i>antivitamins</i>	substances that prevent a living cell from using vitamins. They break down vitamins, turning them into an inactive form; although chemically similar to vitamins, it has the opposite biological effect.

V. CONCLUSION

Apparently, international terms with the prefix "anti" are very important. It is also very important for the science of medicine and plays an important role in the proper organization of treatment. Therefore, from a comparative point of view, the definition of the lexical-terminological feature of this prefix serves to define the important tasks of linguistics.

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